

SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT OF ACECLOFENAC USING LIQUISOLID COMPACT TECHNIQUE

Shweta Vijaywargiya*, Dr. Ravi Kant Sharma

Department of Pharmaceutics, Oriental College of Pharmacy, Indore (M.P) India.

Article Received on 29 October 2025,
Article Revised on 19 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17733636>

*Corresponding Author

Shweta Vijaywargiya

Department of Pharmaceutics, Oriental
College of Pharmacy, Indore (M.P)
India.

How to cite this Article: Shweta Vijaywargiya*, Dr. Ravi Kant Sharma. (2025). Solubility Enhancement Of Aceclofenac Using Liquisolid Compact Technique. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 759–772.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Liquisolid compact technique is a novel concept for delivery of drug through oral route. This approach of delivering drug is mostly suitable for lipophilic drug and poorly or water insoluble drugs. The main objective of present study was to increase the solubility of water in soluble BSc class II drug aceclofenac. Aceclofenac is alipophilic drug that is practically insoluble in water and exhibit an excessively slow dissolution rate in class II compound in biopharmaceutics classification system. The liquid solid compacts were prepared using PEG 400 as non volatile solvent, microcrystalline cellulose as carrier, aerosil 200 as coating material and Sodium starch glycolate was used as super disintegrating agent. Several formulations of liquid solid compacts having different drug concentration in PEG 400 (non volatile solvent) with varying ratio of career to coating material were prepared. The liquid solid compacts were evaluated for Bulk characterization, Flow

properties, solubility studies, drug content, FTIR studies, and in vitro drug release studies. The saturated solubility studies and in vitro drug release studies shows that the increase in solubility of drug and enhanced drug release rate in liquisolid compacts compared to pure drug. The Formulation F5 and F4 is considered as best formulation as it has shown highest drug release in short time (1 hr). Our studies showed that the solubility of the drug can be significantly enhanced with increase in the carrier content there is increase in the solubility resulting and enhanced drug release rate.

KEYWORDS: Liquisolid compacts, Aceclofenac, carrier material, coating material Solubility enhancement, in vitro drug release.

INTRODUCTION

The enhancement of dissolution profile, absorption efficiency and bio availability of water insoluble drugs is one of the major concern of present Pharmaceutical research. Different techniques are employed to enhance the dissolution of poorly soluble drugs like use of water soluble salt and polymorphic forms, solid dispersion, reducing particle size to increase the surface area, pH adjustment, co-precipitation, polymer modification Lyophilization, microencapsulation, liquid solid Technology. Liquisolid compacts technique is one of the novel and most promising technique for promoting drug dissolution rate and efficacy of poorly soluble or water insoluble drugs. The term “liquisolid medication” implies oily liquid drug and solution or suspensions of water insoluble solid drugs carried in suitable non volatile solvent system. By using this formulation technique liquid medication may be may be transformed into a free flowing, readily compressible dry powder by simple physical blending with selected excipients referred to as the carrier and coating materials.^[1,2]

Aceclofenac is an oral non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (nsaid) that has marked anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties that are used to treat osteoarthritis, rheumatism and ankylosing spondylitis. This is reported to have high anti-inflammatory action or minimal comparable effects than traditional nsaid in double-blind studies. Aceclofenac powerful prevents psychlo-oxyase enzymes (cox) that is involved in the synthesis of prostaglandins, which are inflammatory mediators that cause pain, inflammation, inflammation, and fever.^[3]

The main objective of the study is to investigate the possibility of improving the solubility and in vitro drug release rate of Aceclofenac. liquisolid compacts were formulated by using PEG 400 as non volatile solvent, microcrystalline cellulose as carrier, aerosil 200 as coating material and Sodium starch glycolate was used as super disintegrating agent. The in vitro drug release profile of liquisolid compacts was compared with that of pure drug. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and Fourier transform infra-red (FTIR) was performed to ensure that there was no possible introduction between drug and excipients.^[4]

MATERIALS AND METHOD

1. MATERIALS

Aceclofenac was received as a gift sample from Glenmark pharmaceuticals limited (pithampur). Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400) was procured from central drug house (P) LTD (NewDelhi). Microcrystalline cellulose(MCC) From SdFine-chem. limited (Mumbai). Sodium Starch glycolate(SSG) from Qualichems (vadodara). Aerosil from Fine- chem. limited (Mumbai). All other solvent and reagent are used was of analytical grade.

2. EXPERIEMENTALS

2.1 Identification of drug

A. Determination of lamda max was done by UV Spectrophotometric method using Shimadzu Spectrophotometer UV-1800 (Shimadzu Corp. Japan).

The solution was then diluted to a 1:10 ratio with phosphate buffer 7.4 pH (1000 µg/ml). The medication was measured and combined with a liquid that had a specific pH level and a predetermined quantity of the drug. Then, some of the liquid was taken and appropriate dilutions were made with phosphate buffer 6. The concentration of 10 µg/ml was measured using a spectrophotometer, which scanned in the UV range of 200-400nm. This data was then used for analysis and a spectrum was recorded. Solubility of aceclofenac was determined in distilled water and various non-aqueous solvents like methanol, ethanol, hcl, chloroform, phosphate buffer 7.4, and phosphate buffer 4.2.^[7] The UV spectra of aceclofenac drug are shown in fig. 2.

B. Melting point

The melting point of the drug sample was determined by utilizing a melting point apparatus. The tube was submerged in a water bath set at 37°C for a duration of 30 minutes. A minuscule quantity of the medication was inserted into a slender tube measuring approximately 10-12 cm in length and having a diameter of 1mm. The tube had a hole at one end, so we inserted a smaller tube into a machine that melts things and heated it up. Then we put some drug powder in the tube and saw how hot it had to get for the powder to melt. We wrote down the temperature when that happened.^[6] The melting point of Aceclofenac is shown in the table 3.

D. Preparation of standard Calibration curve of Aceclofenac

To make a standard solution of aceclofenac, we added 100 mg of the drug to 100 ml of a buffer that had 1000 µg of the drug per ml. Then, we added more buffer to make the total

volume 100 ml. Possible To make different amounts of a solution, we took 0. 5, 1. 0, 1. 5, 2. 0, 2. 5, 3. 0, 3. 5, and 4. 0 milliliters of the solution and mixed them Absorbance was noted using UV-VIS Spectrophotometer at 276 nm against blank (phosphate buffer 7. 4).^[7] The calibration curves of aceclofenac are shown in fig 4.

E. Solubility studies of drug

Solubility of aceclofenac was determined in distilled water and various non-aqueous solvents like methanol, ethanol, hcl, chloroform, phosphate buffer 7.4, and phosphate buffer 4.2. 6: The results showed that aceclofenac was highly soluble in methanol and ethanol, moderately soluble in hcl, and insoluble in chloroform and phosphate buffer. Aceclofenac can dissolve well in methanol and ethanol, but not much in hcl ten mg of drug was dissolved in 10 ml of solvent taken in conical flask. To find out how much solute is in each solvent. The solvents were shaken at 25oc for 24 hrs. After shaking, the samples were examined for the presence of any dissolved, suspended particles and clarity.^[8] Results are disclosed in the table 5.

2.4 Method of preparation of liquisolid compact

a) Formulation of liquisolid compact using selected non volatile solvent, carrier and coating material

For the preparation of liquisolid compact of aceclofenac, preparation of drug solution to make a solid form of aceclofenac, a non volatile solvent is selected for dissolving the drug from the results of solubility studies, a powder made of peg 400, microcrystalline cellulose, and aerosil pH 200 the right amounts of drug and peg 400 were measured and put in a beaker and then mixed well, until the drug was evenly distributed in the solution. Selected amounts (w) of the resultant liquid medications were incorporated into calculated quantities of carrier contained in the mortar.^[9]

The formulation of liquisolid compact of Aceclofenac includes two steps as follow:

a) Preparation of drug solution

For the preparation of liquisolid compact of Aceclofenac, Preparation of drug solution to make a solid form of Aceclofenac, a non volatile solvent is selected for dissolving the drug from the results of solubility studies, A powder made of PEG 400, Microcrystalline cellulose, and Aerosil pH 200 The right amounts of drug and PEG 400 were measured and put in a beaker and then mixed well, until the drug was evenly distributed in the solution. Selected

amounts (W) of the resultant liquid medications were incorporated into calculated quantities of carrier contained in the mortar.^[10]

b) Mixing

The mixing procedure was conducted in three stages. During the first stage, the system was blended at an approximate mixing rate of one rotation/ sec for approximately one minute in order to evenly distribute the liquid medication into the powder.

The system was then agitated for 30 minutes at a speed of 200 revolutions per minute. The system was combined with a specific quantity of coating material for a duration of 2 minutes. After that, it was mixed for 30 minutes at a speed of 200 revolutions per minute. The liquid/powder mixture was evenly distributed as a uniform layer on the surfaces of mortar and left undisturbed for about 5 minutes to allow the solution to be absorbed by the particles within the mixture.^[10]

Table 1: composition of optimized liquisolid system.

Formulation Code	Aceclofenac (drug)	Non volatile solvent (PEG400)	Carrier material (MCC)	Coating material(Aerosil)	Super disintegrant (SSG)
F1	100 mg	100 mg	220 mg	10 mg	20 mg
F2	100 mg	100 mg	225 mg	10 mg	15 mg
F3	100 mg	110 mg	220 mg	10 mg	20 mg
F4	100 mg	110 mg	225 mg	10 mg	15 mg
F5	100 mg	120 mg	220 mg	10 mg	20 mg
F6	100 mg	120 mg	225 mg	10 mg	15 mg

3. Evaluation of liquisolid compacts

3.1. Bulk characterisation of liquisolid systems

Bulk characterisations of liquisolid system were estimated by Bulk density, Tapped density, Carr's index, and Hausner's ratio. The flow property was determined by Angle of repose. These properties were determined by using the following equations:^[11]

Bulk Density = Mass (g)/ bulk volume

Tapped density= Mass (g)/tapped volume

Carr's index= Tapped density- bulk density/ tapped density X 100

Hausner's ratio= tapped density/ bulk density

Angle of repose= $\tan^{-1}(h/r)$.

The bulk characterisation and flow properties of liquisolid compacts were recorded in table 6.

3.2. Determination of saturation solubility of liquisolid system

Solubility study was performed according to method reported by Higuchi and Connors. The liquisolid compact system F1,F2,F3,F4,F5,F6 were added in 10 ml distilled water taken in stoppered conical flask and were shaken for 24 hrs at $37^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 1$ in orbital shaker. Two ml aliquots were withdrawn at 1 hr intervals and filtered through whatman filter paper. The filtered solution were analysed spectrophotometrically at 276 nm against blank.^[11] The saturation solubility of liquisolid system is shown in fig 7.

3.3. Drug content of liquisolid systems

The liquisolid systems equivalent to unit dose of drug was weighed accurately and dissolved in 100 ml of phosphate buffer 7.4 and filtered through whatman filter paper. The solution were analysed by UV spectrophotometer at 276 nm and drug content calculated accordingly.^[12] The drug content of various formulations were recorded in table 8.

3.4. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

Fourier transform infrared was conducted using shimadzu 8300 spectrometer and the spectrum was recorded in the region of $4000\text{-}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The procedure consisted of placing a sample powder dispersed in KBr (200-400 mg) and compressed into a disc by applying a pressure of 5 tons for 5 min in a hydraulic press. The pellet was placed in the light path and the spectrum was obtained. The drug and excipients were scanned individually as well as combined from in order to find the drug – excipient interaction.^[12] The IR Spectra of pure drug, carrier and formulations are shown in fig 9.

3.5. In vitro drug release studies

The in vitro drug release studies of liquisolid system was performed by using (USP type II apparatus Rotating paddle type) at rotation speed of 50 rpm in distilled water as a dissolution media at 37°C was used for invitro drug release studies. One capsule was used in each test, accurately weighed amount of liquisolid compacts was filled in capsule and immersed in dissolution medium consisting of 900 ml of phosphate buffer 7.4 at 37°C . An aliquots 5ml from dissolution medium was withdrawn at specified times intervals (5,10,15,30,45,60 minutes) and replacing the same amount with the fresh medium in order to keep the total volume constant. The sample was filtered through whatman filter paper and assayed by measuring the absorbance at 276 nm using the UV-visible spectrophotometer.^[14] The in vitro release of various formulations are shown in fig 11,12,13.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. UV Spectroscopy

Peaks were obtained at 276 which shows that drug is pure.

Fig. 2: Lamda max of Aceclofenac.

4.2. Melting point

The melting point of drug sample was determined by using melting point apparatus. As given in the reference. The melting point of aceclofenac is shown in the table: 3.

Table 3: Melting Point of Aceclofenac.

Drug	Observed	Reference
Aceclofenac	149 ⁰ C	149-153 ⁰ C

4.3. Preparation of standard Calibration curve of Aceclofenac in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 (λ_{max} 276 nm)

Calibration curve of Aceclofenac was prepared in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 at 276 nm. The absorbance values (mean of three determinations) with their standard deviation at different concentration in the range of 5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for phosphate buffer pH 7.4 are tabulated. The drug obeys Beer's Lambert law in the concentration range. Linear regression analysis for all calibration curves of Aceclofenac is given in Table.5.3.4 So, this equation was used for the calculation of the solubility of the drug in different solvent, drug content and drug release.

Fig. 4: Calibration curve of aceclofenac in Phosphate buffer 7.4.

4.4 Determination of solubility of aceclofenac in different solvents: solubility analysis for drug aceclofenac was determined in different solvents. Results are disclosed in the table 5.

Table No. 5: Solubility data of Aceclofenac in different mediums.

Solvent (5 ml)	Solubility of drug (5mg)
Distilled water	Insoluble
0.1 N HCL	Slightly soluble
7.4 pH Buffer	Slightly soluble
Ethanol	Slightly soluble
Methanol	Poorly soluble
Chloroform	Poorly soluble
Acetone	Insoluble

4.5. Bulk Characterization of Liquisolid Compact systems

The bulk density of various formulations were found to be between 0.365-0.415, tapped density between 0.418-0.467, hausner's ratio between 1.15- 1.17, carr's index between 11.09-14.09, which shows the good compressibility index of formulations. The angle of repose was determined to be between 25.20-28.50 degrees, indicating the excellent flow characteristics of the formulation. The table displays the outcomes of various measurements, including tapped density, angle of repose, carr's index, and hausner's ratio.

Table 6: Determination of flow properties of liquisolid powder.

Batch code	Bulk density(g/cm ³)	Tapped density(g/cm ³)	Hausner's ratio	Carr's ratio%	Angle of repose
F1	0.365	0.418	1.17	14.01	25.2 ⁰
F2	0.367	0.416	1.15	13.02	26.06 ⁰
F3	0.405	0.460	1.14	14.09	26.35 ⁰
F4	0.392	0.448	1.13	12.01	26.95 ⁰

F5	0.395	0.455	1.15	12.10	28.90 ⁰
F6	0.415	0.467	1.12	11.09	27.60 ⁰

4.7. Determination of saturation solubility

Saturation solubility studies were conducted for both pure drug and prepared liquisolid compacts. From the result of saturation solubility studies it was observed that there was an increase in solubility of drug in liquisolid compact system as compared to pure drug. With increase in the concentration of carriers solubility of drug increased and the liquisolid compacts containing microcrystalline cellulose and sodium starch glycolate in (f4) and (f5) has increased the solubility up to five times. This enhances its wetting ability, leading to a substantial rise in solubility. The saturation solubility of various formulations are recorded in fig 7.

Fig. 7: Solubility graph of batches F1 to F6.

4.8. Drug content of liquisolid systems

The drug content estimation was performed to ensure uniform distribution of drug. The drug content of liquisolid compact of aceclofenac was performed for all the prepared formulations. The result indicates that the drug content in all the formulations was found uniform between 84% to 97% which was scanned spectrophotometrically at λ_{\max} 276 nm. The drug content of various formulations is recorded in table 8.

Table 8: Drug content of various formulations.

S.NO	Formulation Code	% Drug content
1.	F1	84%
2.	F2	92%
3.	F3	86%
4.	F4	95%
5.	F5	97%
6.	F6	93%

4.9. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

The compatibility studies for the drug excipients were conducted following the procedure outlined in 6.1. The frequency spectra of aceclofenac, aceclofenac + f5, are presented in figures 6.3.5 and 6.3.6 respectively. Pure aceclofenac exhibited significant absorption at 2107.1, 1918.1, 1848.6, 1771.5, 1714.6, and 664.4 cm^{-1} , with the major peaks being observed at these specific wavelengths. The findings showed no difference in the peak levels of aceclofenac when it was combined with excipients compared to when it was administered alone.

Fig. 9: FTIR spectrum of aceclofenac (ACE).

Fig. 10: IR spectra of liquisolid formulation (F5).

E. In vitro drug release studies

The in vitro drug release profile of pure drug aceclofenac, liquisolid compacts in dissolution medium are shown in figure (11, 12, 13). The liquisolid compacts of aceclofenac exhibited a substantial rise in the drug release compared to pure aceclofenac. In the liquisolid formulations f1 and f2 showing 92.93% and 96.27% drug release, f3 and f4 showing 87.28% and 96.62 % drug release, and f5 and f6 showing 97.26% and 85.38% drug release respectively. The formulation exhibited a better drug release rate compared to the pure form of aceclofenac.

Fig. 11: Comparison of In- vitro release of pure Aceclofenac & F1,F2 Batches.

Fig. 12: Comparison of In- vitro release of pure Aceclofenac & F3, F4 Batches.

Fig. 13: Comparison of In-vitro release of pure Aceclofenac & F5, F6 Batches.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author is thankful to the management of Oriental college of pharmacy Indore. For providing necessary facilities to carry out the research work and heartily thankful to my guide Dr. Ravikant Sharma for providing all the support and encouragement to carry out this studies.

CONCLUSION

- It can be concluded that by the use of the designed experimental technique solubility of poorly soluble drug can be improved by using novel liquisolid technique
- This technique is particularly effective for the formulation of poorly soluble drugs belonging to classes ii and iv. This straightforward and efficient technique can be applied on a large scale in industrial settings.
- This is an economical technique it does not involve any specialized equipment for production, yet very effective tool for enhancement of dissolution rate of poorly soluble drugs.
- It is a very successful and simple method to enhance the aqueous solubility and dissolution rate. A: the type and material of the coating and carrier affected how fast the drug dissolved.
- The use of non volatile solvent in the formulation of liquisolid compact cause increased wettability of water insoluble drug aceclofenac.
- Drug release data reveals due to presence of liquisolid formulation there is increase in drug release profile and enhance solubility compare to the pure drug.

REFERENCE

1. Spireas S. Liquisolid System and method of preparing same. U.S Patent 6423339B1, 2002.
2. Lean lachman, Herbert A, Liberman and Joseph L karnig The theory and practice of industrial pharmacy. 3rd ed. Lea and Febigen, Philadelphia, 1986; 301-302.
3. Satheeshbabu N, Gowthamarajan K, Gayathri R and Saravanan, "Liquisolid: A Novel Technique To Enhance Bioavailability." J. Pharm. Res., 2011; 4(1): 181-185.
4. Nokhodchi, A., Hentzschel, C.M. and Leopold, C.S., Drug release from liquisolid systems: speed it up, slow it down. Expert opinion on drug delivery, 2011; 8(2): 191-205.
5. Tikariya Komal, Agrawal Shikha, Formulation and Evaluation of Liquisolid Compact of Etoricoxib for solubility Enhancement, Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Medicine (IJPSM), June- 2019; 4(6): 1-18.
6. M.-A. Molaei, Karim Osouli-Bostanabad, Khosro Adibkia, Javad Shokri, Solmaz Asnaashari and Yousef Jav, Enhancement of keto conazole dissolution rate by theliquisolidtechnique, Acta Pharm, 2018; 68: 325– 336. (2.1)

7. Dhanashri B. Hire, Rajendra K. Surawase, Yashpal M. More and Avish D. Maru. Formulation And Evaluation of Liquisolidcompact Of Telmisartan, World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2018; 7(7): (2.2)
8. Dhananjay Ahir, Rajeshree Panigrahi, Prasanta Kumar Choudhury and Ajit Kumar, Formulation And Evaluation of Telmisartan Liquisolid Compact Tablets International Journal of Pharma And Chemical Research I Volume 4 I Issue 3 I Jul – Sep I 2018 (2.3)
9. J.Ramesh, B. vijaya kumara, and Y. narsimha reddy Formulation and evaluation of olanzapine liquisolid compact tablet,International Journal Of Pharmacy & Technology IJPT| June-2016 | Vol. 8 | Issue No.2 | 11780-11789 Page 11781(2.7)
10. Jamakandi VG, Kerur SS and Patil US, Formulation and Evaluation of Immediate Release Tablet of Carvedilol using Liquisolid Compacts Technique for Solubility Enhancement Asian Journal of Pharmaceutics • Jul-Sep 2016 (2.8)
11. Prajila A. Vipin KV, Chandran SC, Premletha K and Augusthy AR, Formulation and evaluation of Deflazacort liquisolid tablets Int J Res Pharm Sci., 2016, 6(1): 19 – 25 (2.9)
12. Vemula SK, Radhika K Liquisolid Compact Technique for Improvement of the Dissolution Rate of Flurbiprofen: Formulation and Evaluation J Drug Res Dev., 2015; 1(1) (2.10)
13. Shamili Kaparathi and P.R Sethas, Risperidone liquisolid compacts–Formulation and evaluation Pelagia Research Library Der Pharmacia Sinica, 2015, 6(6): 9-15 (2.11)
14. Mowafaq M. Ghareeb et al Liquisolid compact as an approach for Tenoxicam solubility enhancement using tween 80 as liquid vehicle J. Chem. Pharm. Res., 2015; 7(10): 379-393 (2.12)